

Table 1. The main characteristics of Ai-chiao-nan-te, Ai-tsai-chan, and Dee-geo-woo-gen.^a China.

Designation	Origin	Maturity (days to heading)	Plant (cm)	Panicles (no./plant)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain/panicle	Hulled grains		
							Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Length-width ratio
Ai-chiao-nan-te	Chao-yang County, Kwangtung Province	Early (73 days)	75.9	18.2	26.8	101.0	8.6	3.1	2.77
Ai-tsai-chan	Junghsien County, Kwangsi Province	Medium (101 days)	94.9	18.7	24.6	154.9	8.6	3.2	2.69
Dee-geo-woo-gen	Taiwan or Fukien Province	Medium-late (107 days)	102.0	15.3	27.1	161.8	8.3	3.2	2.59

^a Seeded on 11 March and transplanted on 11 April. Plant spacing = 40 x 20 cm.

Ai-chiao-nan-te, Ai-tsai-chan, and Dee-geo-woo-gen, have been used in the breeding of almost all modern high yielding rice varieties (Table 2). ■

Genetic analysis of dwarfism in Chinese rices

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Parnell and associates were the earliest (1922) to conduct genetic analysis on rice dwarfism. In 1925 Akemine carried out a detailed genetic analysis of three dwarf mutants — Daikoku, Ebisu, and Kodaikoku—which had been isolated from the normal variety Akage. He pointed out that tallness was dominant to dwarfness and that the three dwarf mutants resulted from the interaction between two pairs of complementary genes. That type of dwarf mutant still cannot be used in breeding programs because of complicated inheritance and undesirable traits.

Semidwarfs used as parent materials in current rice breeding programs are generally about 75 to 100 cm tall. I shall present some of my genetical research work on dwarfism. Between 1976 and 1977, three semidwarf varieties were crossed with the same tall male parent. Leng-shiu-ma (a local variety from Hunan Province).

The height of the F₂ populations of the three crosses was greater than the

Table 2. The genealogical relations among the Chinese semidwarfs.

Important varieties	Direct or indirect derivatives of
Kwang-chang-ai, Chen-chu-ai, Kwang-lu-ai 4, Nanking 11	Ai-tsai-chan
Lung-Ke 113, Kwang-Hsuan 3, Te-ku-ai 31	Ai-chiao-nan-te
Er-chiu-ai, Hung-mei-Tsao, Er-chiu-nan 1	Both Ai-chiao-nan-te and Ai-tsai-chan
TN1, Taichung Sen 2, Kaohsiung Sen 2	Dee-geo-woo-gen ^a

^a Virtually all semidwarf varieties developed at IRRI and in national rice improvement programs are also derivatives of Dee-geo-woo-gen.

mean height of their parents, but slightly less than that of the tall parent (Table 1), which shows the incomplete dominance of tallness.

The variation in plant height among F₂ populations of the various crosses was continuous, but all F₂ populations were characterized by a bimodal distribution.

Table 1. Plant height of F₁ and parents of various crosses.

Cross	Plant ht (cm)						Expression
	Female parent		F ₁ Male		parent		
	n	\bar{x}	n	\bar{x}	n	\bar{x}	
Ai-chino-nan-te/Leng-shui-ma	10	77.0	5	129.1	10	136.7	incomplete dominance
Ai-tsai-chan/Leng-shui-ma	10	68.0	8	125.6	10	136.7	"
Dee-geo-woo-gen/Leng-shui-ma	10	83.0	7	130.3	10	136.7	"

Table 2. The segregation ratio of plant height in F₂ of various crosses. Kwangchow, 1977.

Cross	Plants (no.)			Ratio (T:D)	X ²	P
	Tall form	Dwarf form	Total			
Ai-chiao-nan-te/Leng-shui-ma	210	62	272	3:1	0.75	0.50–0.30
Ai-tsai-chan/Leng-shui-ma	202	70	212	3:1	0.08	0.80–0.70
Dee-geo-woo-gen/Leng-shui-ma	210	62	272	3:1	0.75	0.50–0.30

So two rather distinct classes were considered to exist within the population.

Furthermore, transgressive segregation for plant height was observed in the F₂ population of various crosses. The occurrence of transgressive individuals indicates that, besides the major gene, some modifiers control semidwarfism.

Those modifiers may exhibit positive or negative action. Segregation and recombination among modifiers result in the appearance of transgressive individuals.

The segregation between tall and dwarf forms in various crosses, when tested by *chi* square, coincides with a

3:1 ratio (Table 2). That indicates that the semidwarfism of Ai-chiao-nan-te, Ai-tsai-chan. and Dee-geo-woo-gen is largely conditioned by a single pair of recessive genes. Our results agree with IRRI's findings of 1964-65.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Grain quality

A note on alkali test of rice using a petri dish

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The alkali-degradation test is popular for evaluation of rice quality. In the original method that Little, Hilder, and Dawson developed in 1958, a special plastic box was used in conducting the test. But because the boxes were neither easily available nor essential, researchers generally use a pair of petri dishes instead. The differences in geometry and size, however, require that the volume of KOH solution to use with the petri dish be carefully considered — a point that researchers have often ignored.

Three aspects should be considered: 1) the volume of alkali solution per grain, 2) the depth of alkali in the container, and 3) the surface area available per grain. Attention has usually been paid only to the first aspect, which is erroneous.

The scores of several rice samples in 7-cm-diameter petri dishes were compared with those obtained with the use of the original Little et al (1958) method, the revised Bhattacharya and Sowbhagya (1972) method, and several possible alternatives (see table). The scores in methods IV-A and IV-B were essentially lower than those in the two reference methods (I and II). The scores of the rest were essentially identical. The depth of alkali solution in the container is clearly the crucial factor. Once the

depth is optimal, the volume of alkali per grain can vary fairly widely with no effect.

The other consideration is the available surface area per grain. In the revised procedure of Bhattacharya and Sowbhagya, the total diameter of the degraded grain mass is an important scoring criterion. In the final stages of degradation (scores 5-8), the degraded grain mass assumes a mean diameter of about 20 mm. To score by this method, therefore, sufficient area (πr^2) must be available for each grain to occupy a space of about 3.14 cm². Allowing for vacant intergrain space, that means that a

7-cm-diameter dish can accommodate not more than 7 (or at most 8) grains (see figure). That is why methods I, IV-C, V, and VII gave essentially identical extents of grain degradation, but were nevertheless insufficient for correct scoring of samples showing high degradation. In the limited space available, the collars merged so the correct mass diameter could not be measured.

It was concluded that for interlaboratory comparison using petri dishes of varying sizes for the alkali test, the two essential conditions are: 1) that sufficient alkali solution is added to maintain a liquid depth of 4.5 mm in the

Comparison of alkali test results under different test conditions^a, Karnataka, India.

Testing method	Test condition					Result ^a
	KOH used (ml)	Grains (no.)	Depth of KOH (mm)	MIKOH/grain	Cm ² /grain	
I. Original box method ^b	10	6	4.4	1.7	3.8	(OK)
Petridish methods ^c						
II. Reference method ^d	20	6	5.0	3.3	6.7	OK
III. Excess alkali/grain	20	3	5.0	6.7	13.3	OK
IV. Volume/grain constant						
A	10	6	2.5	1.7	6.7	No
B	15	9	3.8	1.7	4.5	No
C	20	12	5.0	1.7	3.3	(OK)
V. Area/grain constant	20	10	5.0	2.0	4.0	(OK)
VI. KOH depth/grain constant	18	6	4.5	3.0	6.7	OK
VII. Volume, area, depth constant	18	10	4.5	1.8	4.0	(OK)
VIII. Suggested	18	7	4.5	2.5	5.7	OK

^aOK = gives correct score; (OK) = correct at low scores, but incorrect at high scores for the available area is insufficient for optimal spreading; No = score is too low.

^bLittle, Hilder, and Dawson (Cereal Chem. 35, 111, 1958). Plastic box 4.75 × 4.75 × 0.75 cm used. Total area, 23 cm².

^cPetri dish with a 7-cm diameter was used. Total area is 40 cm². Volume refers to that of the alkali solution. Constant means condition identical to that in the original box method.

^dBhattacharya and Sowbhagya (J. Food Technol. 7, 323, 1972).